

Dental intervention using GA for managing a child with Frankel's definitely negative behaviour

Aarti Garg*, Hemant Jain**¹, Sunada Das[□], Sonali Saha[◇] and Abhay Mani Tripathi[◇]

*Department of Pedodontics and Preventive Dentistry, Jaipur Dental College, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India., **Department of Pediatrics, Journal of clinical and diagnostic research., [□]Department of Oral Medicine and Radiology, Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research., [◇]Department of Pedodontics and Preventive Dentistry, Sardar Patel Post Graduate Institute of Dental and Medical Science, Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh, India.

ABSTRACT To pursue dental treatment in a child needs an extra effort due to the need for behaviour modification techniques; especially in children who require extensive dental procedures. In cases where the non-pharmacological techniques fail, the pharmacological aspect is sought after. General anaesthesia (GA) comes to rescue in such cases. The advent of general anaesthesia (GA) in pediatric dentistry has been researched a lot and found to be effective. However, its use has not been reported much in literature.

We at this moment report a case of 4 years -old child (Frankel's definitely negative behaviour), who was treated successfully under GA. He had multiple decayed teeth and required extraction as well as conservative treatment. Pulpectomy of multiple teeth was performed along with the fabrication of a band and loop space maintainer and aesthetic space maintainer.

KEYWORDS Frankel's definitely negative behaviour, pharmacological behaviour management, Pulpectomy, space maintainer

Introduction

Pediatric dental procedures under general anaesthesia (GA) can be performed in a hospital or an ambulatory setting, and dental offices provided that the facilities are adequate. There are definite criteria for indications of GA and guidelines for choosing patients, policies for health care quality and safety measures in children requiring dental treatments under GA [1,2].

Researches prove that parents and children show positive oral hygiene behaviour after undergoing dental procedures under GA[3,4]. In children, there are behavioural constraints, and so sedation is enhanced by bolus oral administration, unlike adults where sedation depth is titrated through intravenous drug administration[5]. Local anaesthesia as an adjunct to GA has also been recommended as it helps in hemorrhagic control,

physiologic balance maintenance and reduces post-operative pain.[6,7]

There are publications which support the use of GA to perform more extractions and fewer restorative procedures and vice versa [8-10]

Figure 1: Pre-operative intraoral photographs showing the multiple decayed teeth.

Case report

A 4-year-old male patient, accompanied by his mother visited for a dental consultation, with a complaint of pain and swelling due to multiple decayed teeth, for the last six months. It was difficult to examine the child as he was young and exhibited Frankel's definitely negative behaviour. After a lot of efforts, the child was convinced, and his intraoral examination was done, which revealed multiple carious teeth. Most of the teeth (51, 52,

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¹Below Punjab National Bank, GT Road, Delhi 110007, India.; Email: drhemantjain@jcdcr.net

Figure 2: Pre-operative Orthopantamogram showing the pulp involvement of the teeth.

Figure 3: The child after intubation.

Figure 5: Pulpectomy in mandibular anterior.

Figure 6: Intraoral images and radiographs showing Pulpectomy of 75.

Figure 4: Pulpectomy in maxillary anterior.

Figure 7: Extracted root-stumps of 74, 84.

Figure 8: Band and loop Space maintainers about 84,85.

Figure 9: Postoperative orthopantomography.

Figure 10: Fixed functional space maintainer in place and the photograph of the happy child.

61, 62, 63, 71, 72, 73, 75, 81, 82) had pulpal exposure, and almost all teeth had various degree of decay (fig 1). The patient was counselled for an OPG, which revealed pulp involvement in relation to 51,52,61,62,63,71,72,73,74,75,81,83,84,85. Of these, 74 and 84 were grossly decayed, and only root stumps were present (fig 2).

The parents were explained regarding the oral health of the child, and after they consented, the treatment was planned to be done under general anaesthesia. The plan was to include pulpectomy in the teeth that had pulpal involvement, extraction of the grossly decayed ones and fabrication of space maintainers as part of rehabilitation. The child was referred to a paediatrician and an anesthesiologist for checkup and consent. He was admitted a night before the fixed date and was instructed to be NPO for 8 hours. The following drugs were used for the induction of anaesthesia, dosage based on the child's weight - Glycopyrrolate (anticholinergic), Midazolam (procedural sedation), fentanyl (analgesic and tranquillizer), propofol (decreases level of consciousness and lack of memory for events), vecuronium (muscle relaxant), isoflurane (inhalational anaesthesia) and neostigmine (reversible acetylcholinesterase inhibitor) (fig 3) . Pulpectomy of 51,52,61,62,63,71,72,73,75,81,82 , extraction of 74 and 84 was done, followed by fabrication of a band and loop space maintainer in relation to 84 (fig 4-8). For fixed functional space maintainer the impression was taken, and band adaptation was made on the cast. Acrylic teeth were used. Final delivery of the appliance was done the subsequent day (fig 9,10). Home care instructions, diet counselling and oral hygiene measures were explained to the parents. Recall check-up was scheduled after 1 week, then every 3 months to assess the oral hygiene status, restorations and the space maintainer. But unfortunately, the patient was lost to follow up.

Discussion

Anxiety and non-co-operation should always be expected while considering dental treatment of a child. The onus is upon the concerned dentist, to fulfil all the requirements and without seeding any fear within the child against future dental consultations, if required. Behaviour modification techniques might not always be resourceful and anaesthetizing the child might be the only resort. In the present case, the child was difficult to deal with, could be classified as Frankel's definitely negative behaviour [11]. As per AAPD guidelines treatment under GA is indicated in the patients who cannot co-operate due to a lack of psychological or emotional maturity and/or mental, physical, or medical disability; patients for whom local anaesthesia is ineffective because of acute infection, anatomic variations, or allergy; the extremely uncooperative, fearful, anxious, or uncommunicative child or adolescent; patients requiring significant surgical procedures; patients for whom the use of general anaesthesia may protect the developing psyche and/or reduce medical risk; and patients requiring immediate, comprehensive oral/ dental care. [12] The purpose of this case report is to enlighten the advantage of providing extensive complete oral rehabilitation in a short period and in a single visit, allowing immediate relief of pain even with little or no cooperation from the child. With regards to the cost benefits, treatment under GA apparently seems to carry a higher cost than that of outpatient dental treatment procedures. But one needs to consider the secondary costs too - the loss of working days of parents, loss of days at school for the child and the labour that is required in case of multiple outdoor visits for prolonged dental treatment.[13-16]

In the present case, after performing the pulpectomies in the upper anterior, the fixed functional appliance was planned. Impression was taken, and band adaptation was made on the cast. Further, the wax was done after wire bending. The acrylic tooth was trimmed and used. This appliance was delivered in the next day morning to the patient. A similar technique was used by Shanmugaavel et al. who named it as GRASCE" appliance, in which the severely mutilated anterior root stumps were retained after pulpectomy, and the appliance was delivered [17]. Mandibular anterior teeth were restored by GIC following pulpectomy. Further, left and right mandibular molars were grossly decayed. 74 and 84 were extracted. In 75 pulpectomy was done and crown and loop space maintainer was planned, but due to lack of time, we could not give the crown and loop about 75. On the other hand, after the extraction of 84, band and loop space maintainer was delivered. In this case, the lingual arch was not justified, as the lingual arch is indicated in patients having permanent mandibular anterior [18]. Similarly, in a study conducted by Garg et al., bilateral band and loop/ crown and loop were delivered, and the follow up was done for 6 months [19].

Concluding Remarks

To perform this complex and lengthy treatment would have required multiple sittings, and the parents might have abandoned the treatment midway. Considering GA is always a 'complex' procedure, but the complexity paid off when the child and parent left the hospital with a contented smile.

Competing Interests

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References

1. <http://www.aapd.org/assets/1/7/POHRPCTechBrief2.pdf>
2. Nelson TM, Xu Z. Pediatric dental sedation: challenges and opportunities. *Clin Cosmet Investig Dent*. 2015; 7: 97–106.
3. Stapleton M, Sheller B, Williams B, Mancl L. Combining procedures under general anesthesia. *Pediatr Dent* 2007 29(5): 397-402
4. Lee J, Vann W, Roberts M. A cost analysis of treating pediatric dental patients using general anesthesia versus conscious sedation. *Pediatr Dent* 2000 22(1); 27-32
5. Nelson T, Nelson G. The role of sedation in contemporary pediatric dentistry. *Dent Clin North Am*.2013;57:145–161
6. Townsend JA, Hagan JL, Smiley M. Use of local anesthesia during dental rehabilitation with general anesthesia ; a survey of dentist anesthesiologists *Anesth Prog*. 2014; 61910:11-7
7. Atan S, Ashley P, Gilthorpe MS, Scheer B, Mason C, Roberts G. Morbidity following dental treatment of children under intubation general anesthesia in a day stay unit. *Int J Paediatr Dent*. 2004;14910:9-16

8. Ramazani N. Different aspects of general anesthesia in pediatric dentistry-a review.*Iran J Pediatr*. 2016;26920:e2613
9. Eshghi A, Samani MJ, Najafi NF, Hajiahmadi M. Evaluation of efficacy of restorative dental treatment provided under general anesthesia at hospitalized pediatric dental patients of Isfahan. *Dent Res J*. 2012;9940:478-82
10. Savanheimo N, Vehkalati MM. Five year follow up of children receiving comprehensive dental care under general anesthesia. *BMC Oral Health*. 2014,14:154
11. Wright GZ, Alpern GD, Leake JL. The modifiability of maternal anxiety as it relates to children's cooperative dental behavior .*ASDC J Dent Child*. 1973 Jul-Aug;40(4):265-71.
12. http://www.aapd.org/media/policies_guidelines/g_behavguide.pdf
13. Foster T, Perinpanayagam H, Pfaffenbach A, Certo M. Recurrence of early childhood caries after comprehensive treatment with general anesthesia and follow-up. *J Dent child (chic)*. 73(1). 2006: 25-30.
14. Amin M, Harrison R. Change in parental oral health practices following a child's dental treatment under general anaesthesia. *Eur Arch Paediatr Dent*, 7(2), 2006: 116-120
15. Amin M, Harrison R. A conceptual model of parental behavior change following a child's dental general anesthesia procedure. *Pediatr Dent*. 29(4). 2007: 278-286
16. Rashewsky S, Parameswaran A, Sloane C, Ferguson F, Epstein R. Time and Cost Analysis: Pediatric Dental Rehabilitation with General Anesthesia in the Office and the Hospital Settings.*Anesth Prog*. 2012 Winter; 59(4): 147–153.
17. Shanmugaavel AK, Gurunathan D, Sundaranjan L. Smile Reconstruction for the Preschoolers Using GRASCE Appliance – Two Case Reports. *Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research*. 2016 Aug, Vol-10(8): ZD19-ZD22.
18. Tandon S, Choudhary P. Orthodontic prevention. In: Tandon S, Editor. *Textbook of Pedodontics*. 2nd ed. Hyderabad: Paras Publisher; 2008. p. 446-65.
19. Garg A, Samadi F, Jaiswal JN, Saha S. Metal to resin: A comparative evaluation of conventional band and loop space maintainer with the fibre reinforced composite resin space maintainer in children. *Journal of Indian Society of Pedodontics and Preventive Dentistry* 2014; 32(2).